

STRUCTURE AND TYPES OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *Preschool education organization is considered the first stage of continuous education system. The pre-school education organization takes a leading position in educating and developing children, preparing them for school. Preschool education organizations are the main part of this system and have important tasks of conducting public education. This article provides details about the structure of preschool education organizations in Uzbekistan and their different types.*

Keywords: *structure, type, educational system, preschool educational organizations, management system, educational methods and programs, spiritual and educational development of the student, development of preschool educational organizations, directions of development.*

INTRODUCTION

Preschool education organization is the first stage of the continuous education system and is the most important social ground of the society. The pre-school education organization takes a leading position in educating and developing children, preparing them for school. All types of preschool education organizations in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017 - 2021" No. PQ-2707 dated December 29, 2016 Cabinet of Ministers based on the decision. The content of education in the state preschool education organization is developed based on the state requirements for preschool education and is determined by programs approved or recommended by the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The working procedure of the state preschool education organization and the time of children's stay in this organization are determined by the charter of the state preschool education organization and the decision of the founder.

As a rule, the following work schedule is introduced for a five-day work week in a state preschool education organization:

12 hours;

10.5 hours;

9 hours;

4 hours;

Based on the requirements of the population living in the area where the state preschool education organization is located, a 6-day work week may be introduced in the state preschool education organization or its separate groups. The organization of meals in the state preschool education organization is the responsibility of this organization and must be carried out in accordance with sanitary rules, norms and hygiene regulations. Medical services for children are provided by medical staff of the state pre-school education organization and medical staff of regional health authorities attached to this organization in the prescribed manner. Medical staff together with the staff of the state preschool education organization are responsible for the life, health and physical development of children, the implementation of treatment and prevention

measures, compliance with sanitary rules, norms and hygiene regulations, diet and quality. The procedure for organizing children's life protection and health promotion in state preschool education organizations is determined by the Ministry of Preschool Education and the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Supervision of medical staff of the state pre-school education organization is carried out by regional health authorities. The management of the state pre-school education organization creates the necessary conditions for the medical worker to work (a separate service room, furniture and medical equipment, medicines necessary for providing first aid). The training of medical workers of the state pre-school education organization is carried out free of charge at least once every three years in the training organizations of the healthcare system. According to the decision of the admission commission for the admission of children to the state pre-school education organization, the founders of which are local state authorities, the methodical provision and organization of the activities of pre-school education organizations is provided by district (city) departments in the form given in Appendix 1 of this Regulation. based on referrals.

Admission of children to state pre-school education organizations, the founders of which are other organizations, is carried out according to the procedure determined by their founders. If there are vacancies, preschool educational organizations of this state will accept children on the basis of the contract on the referrals of district (city) departments for the methodical provision and organization of activities of preschool educational organizations possible.

When admitting children to a preschool educational organization:

- Group I and II disabled people;
- children of large families;
- children of military personnel;
- children of students and teachers;

- Children who are truly orphaned and deprived of parental care enjoy the privileges of admission to the state pre-school education organization without any queue. Parents of children using privileges submit the documents that are the basis for the granting of privileges to the admission commission. Heads of state pre-school education organizations provide written information to the admission commission about available vacancies in the state pre-school education organization no later than the first day of each month.

Vacancy information is signed by the head of the state preschool education organization and the head of the state preschool education organization is personally responsible for their accuracy and timely entry.

The number of children in each group of the state preschool educational organization should be at least 20, but not more than 25. Groups are filled with children who have passed from another age group from the end of the school year to the new school year (in June, July, August), and are filled with new students depending on the availability of places.

In the state preschool education organization, the academic year begins on September 2 of each year, ends on June 1 of the following year, and the rehabilitation period continues until the beginning of the new academic year.

Temporarily suspending the admission of children to state preschool education organizations, where the number of students exceeds the capacity of the state preschool education organization. organization is carried out on the basis of the decision of the admission commission under the district (city) departments.

In case the number of pupils is less than the specified norm or conditions for receiving children are created in accordance with sanitary rules, norms and hygiene regulations, the regional state sanitary-epidemiological control center should be informed about the methodical provision and organization of activities of pre-school educational organizations in the district. Children are admitted to state pre-school education organizations with the consent of the admission commission under (city) departments.

In order to prepare children not covered by preschool education for primary education, to develop them intellectually, morally, aesthetically and physically, short-term groups are organized in state preschool education organizations based on a four-hour work schedule. Short-term groups in the state preschool education organization are organized by order of the district (city) department for methodical provision and organization of activities of preschool education organizations. The following short-term groups may operate in the state preschool education organization:

Development group - the number is less than 20, but not more than 25 children aged 3 to 7 years is organized for the purpose of their comprehensive development, adaptation to the group of peers and older children;

"Future student" group - less than 20, but not more than 25 children aged 5 to 7 years, is organized in order to prepare them for school;

Integrated group - for children aged 3 to 7 years, the number of which is less than 15, but not more than 20, adaptation of children to society, regular psychological-medical-pedagogical support for children with mental disabilities, support to them. It is organized for the purpose of education, consultative and methodical support of parents. In this group, together with healthy children, no more than three children diagnosed with "retarded mental development" receive education according to an individual plan;

"Problem child" group - regular psychological-medical-pedagogical support, involvement in the educational process, social adaptation for children with disabilities aged 4 to 7 years, whose number is less than 15, but not more than 20, is organized in order to help parents in organizing education and training of children. In this group there may be healthy children together with disabled children, the number of disabled children (preserved mental maturity) should not be less than 3 people.

Other types of short-term groups can be organized in preschool education organization. Tutors and tutor's assistants are not paid extra for working with sick and disabled children in short-term groups.

The following are sources of funding for short-term group activities:

- State budget funds of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- contribution payments for the period of the pupil's stay in the state preschool education organization;
- sponsored donations of individuals and legal entities; other sources not prohibited by law.
- Pedagogical staff of the state preschool education organization, which includes a short-term group, is responsible for the life and health of children, the forms, methods and means of organizing short-term groups are in accordance with the children's age and mental-physiological capabilities.

The necessary material and technical conditions for preschool children in state preschool education organizations are provided by the founder. The number of short-term groups in the state

preschool education organization is determined by the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional preschool education departments, and the main preschool education department of Tashkent city, taking into account the sanitary rules, norms and hygiene regulations of the population. determined depending on the need and the conditions created to ensure the educational process.

Organization of short-term groups is carried out on the basis of an agreement with the state preschool education organization and parents. In the organization of short-term groups, it is necessary to develop a schedule of staff, the procedure for organizing children's daily activities, a list of children and educational programs.

Preschool education organization is established by the founder and registered in accordance with the procedure established by law. The following:

- state administration bodies;
- local state authorities;
- state executive offices;
- other state organizations may be the founders of the state preschool education organization in accordance with the legislation.

It is organized by the pre-school education organization and registered in accordance with the procedure established by law. The following:

state management bodies, local state authorities, state enterprises, other state organizations may be the founders of state pre-school education organizations in accordance with legislation.

Preschool education organizations are divided into the following types according to the specificity of their work:

- preschool education organizations of general type;
- specialized (for children with various disabilities in physical and mental development);
- sanatorium type (for children who are weak, have experienced various infectious diseases, and have chronic conditions);

The preschool educational organization will have its own charter, bank account number, seal with the image of the National Emblem of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its name, and a stamp with its legal address.

Accreditation of a preschool educational organization is carried out on the basis of certification by the authorized state body.

Preschool education organization provides upbringing, education, supervision and care of children in accordance with established state standards and requirements for preschool education organization, as well as health care.

The content of education in preschool education organizations is determined by programs approved or recommended by the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A preschool educational organization has the right to use its own (author's) program. The procedure for approving such programs is established by the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Preschool educational organization (the group is allowed to operate during the day and evening and day and night.

Education and upbringing of children in the preschool education organization is carried out in the state language and in other languages in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Language".

The organization of meals in the preschool educational organization is entrusted to the preschool educational organization and is carried out in accordance with the sanitary rules and norms approved in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Both medical services for children and medical personnel in the state are provided by medical personnel of the health organization attached to Preschool educational organizations, who, together with the employees of the Preschool educational organization, are responsible for the life, health and physical development of children, they are responsible for the implementation of treatment-prophylactic measures, compliance with sanitary-hygiene standards, food routine and quality.

Supervision of the activities of medical personnel is entrusted to local health authorities. The pre-school educational organization provides a room for the medical worker and creates the necessary conditions for his work. Employees of the preschool education organization in the state receive free medical examinations at health authorities, the expenses for which are determined within the funds allocated by the state. The procedure for organizing the protection of children's life and health in preschool educational organizations is determined by the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan together with the Ministry of Health.

In addition to basic educational programs, additional paid educational services are provided, taking into account the needs of the family, on the basis of agreements concluded with parents or their substitutes for the fulfillment of the goals and tasks stated in the charter of the preschool educational organization. have the right to show. Paid educational services cannot be provided within the framework of the main educational activity financed by the founder.

Participants of the educational process in the state preschool education organization

In the state preschool education organization, children, parents, pedagogical staff and members of the board of trustees are participants in the educational process.

Boards of trustees are established in the state preschool education organization, the procedure for their election and their powers are determined in the charter of the state preschool education organization. The activity of the board of trustees of the state preschool education organization is carried out on the basis of the model charter approved by the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION

When accepting children, the state preschool educational organization must familiarize parents with its charter, agenda, educational programs and other documents. Relations between the state preschool education organization and parents are regulated by the contract. The contract concluded with parents includes the time of children's stay in the state preschool education organization, the rights, obligations and responsibilities of the parties in organizing the educational process.

Parents:

- choose the forms of education for their children, the language of education in the state preschool education organization;

- to demand the creation of necessary conditions for education and upbringing of children in the state pre-school education organization and respect for the personality of the child;

- has the right to pick up children from the state pre-school education organization at his convenience during the day in accordance with the terms of the contract concluded with the organization.

Parents may also have other legal and contractual rights.

Parents are obliged to:

- timely payment of the fee for the period of the child's stay in the state preschool education organization in accordance with the established regulations;
- Strictly monitor children's nutrition, personal hygiene skills formation in them, bring the child to the state pre-school education organization neatly dressed.

Parents may have other obligations in accordance with the law and the contract.

The relationship between the pupil and the employees of the state preschool educational organization is conducted on the basis of mutual cooperation, respect for the child's personality and giving him freedom to develop according to his personal characteristics.

Recruitment of employees to the state pre-school education organization is carried out in accordance with the model staff table, which is approved in the prescribed manner.

Persons with appropriate pedagogical education, professional training and high moral qualities have the right to engage in pedagogical activities in the state preschool educational organization. Persons prohibited from engaging in pedagogic activities by a court verdict or according to a medical opinion are not allowed to engage in this activity. The rights, obligations and privileges of the employees of the state preschool education organization are determined by legal documents, the charter of the state preschool education organization, as well as the labor contract. In conclusion, it should be noted that the duties of the employees are specified in the job description and the network tariff-qualification reference.

Pedagogical staff of the state preschool education organization have the following rights:

- participate in the management of the state preschool education organization in the manner determined by its charter;
- to protect one's professional honor and dignity.

Pedagogical staff may have other rights in accordance with legislation. Pedagogical staff are obliged to:

- implementation of modern educational programs in the educational process;
- creation of conditions for all-round intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children, taking into account advanced foreign experience;
- improving the quality of preschool education by providing children with high professional education;
- observing the teacher's ethics, respecting the child's dignity, protecting children from pressure, educating them in the spirit of respect for labor, parents, and the environment;
- to constantly improve his professional skills and pedagogical skills and improve his qualifications within the specified periods.

Pedagogical staff may take other obligations in accordance with the law.

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